

Quantitative Comparison of Direct and GC-Speciated CI-TOF-MS Measurements

Description of method to quantitatively compare direct chemical ionization time-of-flight mass spectrometric (CI-TOF-MS) measurements with those acquired by combining the CI-TOF-MS with an Aerodyne gas chromatography system equipped with thermal desorption preconcentration (GC-CI-TOF-MS) for isomer resolved speciation of the CI signal.

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To compare CI-TOF-MS (CI-only) and speciated GC-CI-TOF-MS (GC-CI) measurements for analytes that have explicit calibration factors, i.e. you have both a measured GC-CI sensitivity (cts/ppb) and a CI-only sensitivity (cts/s/ppb) of an authentic standard of the analyte of interest, the comparison is relatively straight-forward. Briefly, if the CI sample flow rate and the GC sample collection volume and chromatographic peak width(s) are accounted for, a simple scalar relationship is realized. This relationship is discussed in detail in Section 3.1 of Clafin et al., 2021 (<https://doi.org/10.5194/amt-14-133-2021>).

For compounds without a measured calibration factor, we provide here a description of how the GC-CI and CI-only signals can be quantitatively compared. This method allows the user to apportion how much of the CI-only ion signals are associated with one or more compounds resolved by the GC that contribute to that CI ion signal.

Step One: GC-CI Data

The GC-CI signal output (counts, cts) from TERN analysis software (Aerodyne Research; doi:10.5281/zenodo.6914068) is:

$$Signal_{GC} = cts$$

To compare the GC-CI to the CI-only data, we must account for the preconcentrated GC sample volume, which is a function of the GC sample flow rate and the sample collection time. This can be done by dividing $Signal_{GC}$ by the GC sampling flow rate ($Flow_{GC}$, $cm^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$) and the GC sampling time ($Time_{GC}$, min).

$$\frac{Signal_{GC}}{Preconc. \text{ Sample Volume}} = \frac{Signal_{GC}}{[Flow_{GC}][Time_{GC}]} = \frac{cts}{[cm^3 \text{ min}^{-1}][min]} = \frac{cts}{cm^3}$$

This converts $Signal_{GC}$ into units of counts per volume of sample measured ($cts \text{ cm}^{-3}$). This new value of $Signal_{GC}$ is the GC signal, normalized to the collected sample volume, which can be used to compare to the CI-only signal described below.

$$Signal_{GC} = \frac{cts}{cm^3}$$

Step Two: CI-only Data

The CI-TOF-MS samples ambient air at a constant flow rate to generate the ion signal (counts/second, cts/s):

$$Signal_{CI} = \frac{cts}{s}$$

This signal is dependent on the CI-TOF-MS sample flow rate. To compare the CI-only data to the GC-CI data, the $Signal_{CI}$ can be divided by the CI-TOF-MS sample flow rate ($Flow_{CI}$, $cm^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$).

$$\frac{Signal_{CI}}{Flow_{CI}} = \frac{cts}{[cm^3 \text{ min}^{-1}][s]} \times \frac{60 s}{1 \text{ min}} = \frac{cts}{cm^3}$$

This will convert the $Signal_{CI}$ into units of counts per volume of sample measured ($cts \text{ cm}^{-3}$). This new value of $Signal_{CI}$ is the CI-only signal, normalized to the sample volume, which can be used to compare to the GC-CI signal described above.

$$Signal_{CI} = \frac{cts}{cm^3}$$

Step Three: Corrections for Excess Make-up Flow and Transfer Loss

The above conversions assume that the flow from the GC to the CI-TOF-MS is ideal and no analyte is lost during the transfer.

For example, ideally the CI-TOF-MS would be sampling at a certain rate (e.g. $100 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$), and when sampling from the GC some of this flow would be coming from the column eluent (e.g. $2 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$) and the remainder be supplied from the make-up flow (e.g. $98 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$), creating a perfectly flow balanced system for the GC-CI transfer flow:

$$Transfer \text{ Flow} = GC \text{ eluent} + \text{makeup flow}$$

$$Transfer \text{ Flow} = 2 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ min}^{-1} + 98 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ min}^{-1} = 100 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$$

$$Transfer \text{ Flow} - Flow_{CI} = 0 \text{ sccm}$$

In this case, no correction would be required for the comparison. In reality, some of the $Signal_{GC}$ is lost during this transfer due to an over-dilution of the make-up flow (e.g. $118 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$) to prevent elevated signal background that can occur if the CI inlet is not supplied with adequate overflow:

$$Transfer \text{ Flow} = 2 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ min}^{-1} + 118 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ min}^{-1} = 120 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$$

$$Transfer \text{ Flow} - Flow_{CI} = 120 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ min}^{-1} - 100 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ min}^{-1} = 20 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$$

In this example, only 83% of the GC analyte will be injected into the CI-TOF-MS reaction for detection. To account for this:

$$\frac{Signal_{GC}[Transfer \text{ Flow}]}{Flow_{CI}} = Signal_{GC, \text{Corr}} = \frac{cts}{cm^3}$$

With these conversions, the GC-CI and the CI-only signals can be quantitatively compared:

$$Signal_{CI} = Signal_{GC, \text{Corr}} = \frac{cts}{cm^3}$$